

The Law in Conflict? – The Battle Between the Law of Contract and Tort.

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Abstract

This article examines the potential conflict between contract law and tort law, specifically addressing whether the imposition of reasonable conditions for leaving a supermarket is compatible with the contractual principle of an invitation to treat. It argues that by imposing such conditions, supermarkets limit customers' freedom to voluntarily enter into a contract, thereby undermining consent. The article concludes that the fundamental principles of contract law, particularly the notion of an invitation to treat, should take precedence over claims of false imprisonment. Consequently, individuals should not be obligated to purchase goods as a condition for leaving the premises.

1. Introduction

This article examines the conflict between invitations to treat and false imprisonment in supermarkets, questioning whether the law should permit supermarkets to impose reasonable exit conditions on customers. There is legal ambiguity over whether supermarkets can impose conditions on customers before allowing them to leave. This is significant because invitations to treat form the foundation of contract law, yet it remains uncertain whether the tort of false imprisonment should override these principles in this context. This issue is particularly relevant in supermarkets where automatic gates sometimes fail to open for customers. Customers may experience temporary restrictions on their freedom, particularly given that self-checkout areas are often understaffed.

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This article first examines the fundamental elements of contract law, including invitations to treat, offer, acceptance, and consideration, to establish their role in protecting individuals. It then explores the tort of false imprisonment, focusing on the exception allowing reasonable conditions for exit. Next, we analyse whether there is true freedom of contract or an imbalance of bargaining power in this context. We also consider the public policy implications if tort law were to prevail over contract law, including potential effects on in-person shopping. Finally, while automated gates offer theoretical benefits, we argue that current technology fails to achieve supermarkets' intended goals. We conclude that fundamental principles of contract law should take precedence.

2. The Law

This article is looking purely at the civil law, which is the law governing disputes between private individuals and/or organisations, compared to the criminal legal system where cases are brought by the state in the name of the crown. The civil procedure is “normally activated when one private citizen or enterprise seeks redress for a civil wrong, such as a breach of contract, or a tort.”¹

The criminal law does have a heavy influence in the factual scenario of this article in terms of an individual “appropriat[ing] property belonging to another with the intention of permanently depriving the other of it”, but this article is not concerned with individuals who are carrying out a theft, but rather honest shoppers with no intention to steal any property.²

¹ Penny Darbyshire, ‘Civil Procedure’, in *Darbyshire on the English Legal System* (13th edn, Sweet & Maxwell 2020).

² Theft Act 1968, s 1(1).

Here we are concerned with the law of contract, when will there be an offer and acceptance and also the law of tort looking at the law around false imprisonment and the exceptions around this area of the law.

i. Law of Contract

An offer has been defined as “an expression of willingness to contract on specified terms made with the intention that it is to become binding as soon as it is accepted by the person to whom it is addressed.”³ This basic definition has caused a variety of problems concerning when exactly is there said to be an offer and when that offer has been accepted, which subsequent case law has helped to clarify. For instance, in a shop there is only limited stock so if the offer occurred at the point, we picked something off the shelf, would the shop be in breach of contract if they ran out of the specific product?

In *Carlill v Carbolic Smoke Ball Company* (CBSC), the CBSC manufactured a smoke ball which they claimed prevented the flu.⁴ On an advertising board they stated that anyone who used the smoke ball correctly for two weeks and still caught the flu would be paid £100. The CSBC even said they had deposited £1000 with the Alliance Bank to show their sincerity. Ms Carlill bought a smoke ball, used it correctly but still caught the flu. The question here was whether there had been an offer which Ms Carlill had accepted. The Court of Appeal held that the advertisement did amount to a legal offer and that when the customer bought the smoke ball, this amounted to consideration, the third vital ingredient for a legally binding contract. Jackson summarises Bowen LJ’s argument nicely by saying that although “the offer might have been made to the whole world, but the contract was made only with the individual who came forward and fulfilled the conditions of the offer.”⁵ Therefore, this case clarified that there will

³ Hugh Beale, ‘The Agreement’, in *Chitty on Contracts* (35th edn, Sweet & Maxwell 2023).

⁴ [1893] 1 QB 256.

⁵ Nicola Jackson, ‘*Carlill v Carbolic Smoke Ball Co.* [1893] 1 QB 256’, in *Essential Cases: Contract Law* (6th edn, OUP 2023).

be an offer where there is certainty of terms and an intention to be bound. This intention to be bound is important in this article.

However, it has been held whether that is an offer can also depend on the environment in which the offer is made. In *Blue v Ashley*, the question was whether there was a contract and an intention to be bound in a contract which was entered into in a pub.⁶ Mr Blue was a specialist in investment banking and corporate finance and after a lot of drinking the conversation turned to whether Mr Blue could raise the company's share price from £4 to £8. Mr Ashley told Mr Blue that he would pay him £15 million pounds if Mr Blue managed to raise the share price to this amount. Mr Blue was successful in raising the share price, but the contract was held to be void. The court reasoned that there was no intention to be bound as this was a social occasion rather than a business event and the surroundings of a pub with lots of alcohol made it a very informal setting. There were also problems with the certainty of the terms, for instance there was no agreed standard to measure the performance.

Therefore, this case held that whether there is a contract will largely depend on the type of contract and in what surroundings the contract was discussed and entered into. For a contract to be binding there must be a clear and objective intention to create legal relations. It can be argued that in most social settings there can be no intention to enter legal relations, particularly where alcohol is involved. However, if this is a situation where the objective person would expect to enter legal relations, the contract would likely be valid. For instance, in a shop if we plan to buy something we have an intention to enter legal relations when handing over the money to the cashier, or self-checkout as it may be in these modern times. Similarly, if you are in a pub under the influence of alcohol, any contract with the bar staff to purchase further

⁶ [2017] EWHC 1928.

alcoholic beverages would also likely be seen as completely valid. In summary, one must look at the situation of the parties when they are entering into a contract.

This article is concerned with the law regarding contracts in supermarkets. It can therefore be said in almost all cases that if someone picks up an item in a supermarket and intends to leave the supermarket with the said item, they have an intention to enter a contract to buy this item. This contract is fulfilled with an offer, acceptance and consideration from the payment for the item. However, when does the offer and acceptance occur? If there was an offer as soon as the customer picked an item off the shelf, this customer could not put this item back if they found a cheaper alternative or changed their mind. Furthermore, if an offer occurred at this point the supermarket would be obliged to contract with everyone who picked up this item. This is likely impossible as a supermarket only have limited stock of each product so they could easily find themselves in breach of contract if they were unable to supply the goods.

This problem was answered in the case of the *Pharmaceutical Society of Great Britain v Boots Cash Chemists*, which concerned the display of items on shop shelves.⁷ In this case, the court unanimously agreed with Lord Goddard CJ that an item on a shop shelf was an invitation to treat, which is essentially inviting the individual to buy an item. Lord Goddard CJ explained that:

“the mere fact that a customer picks up a bottle of medicine from the shelves in this case does not amount to an acceptance of an offer to sell. It is an offer by the customer to buy and there is no sale effected until the buyer’s offer to buy is accepted by the acceptance of the price. The offer, the acceptance of the price, and therefore the sale, takes place under the supervision of the pharmacist.”

⁷ [1952] 2 QB 795.

Goddard CJ also used the example of going into a bookshop. In this example, individuals are invited to pick up the books to have a look at the blurb, for instance, but they are not required to then buy that book, and the shop are not obliged to sell the book. The idea that items in a shop are invitations to treat which the buyer offers to buy and the cashier then accepts this offer was confirmed in *Fisher v Bell*, which concerned a ‘flick knife’ which was displayed in a shop window with a price tag.⁸ The Restriction of Offensive Weapons Act 1959 made it illegal to sell such a knife and so the owner was charged under this Act. It was held that the knife was merely an invitation to treat and so the shop owner could not be guilty under this Act.

Therefore, the law of contract essentially says that anyone can walk into a shop and pick up items to look at, and these will be invitations to treat. It is only when we take these items to the cashier that we show an intention to enter legal relations and create a contract. This means that if I cannot find what I went in the shop for, or a book shop does not have the book I was looking for, I can walk out of that shop empty handed with no obligation to buy anything.

ii. Law of Tort

There are three trespass to the person torts. These are battery which is unlawful physical contact, assault which is the threat of violence and false imprisonment, which we are here concerned about. Goff LJ defined false imprisonment in *Collins v Wilcock* as “the unlawful imposition of constraint on another’s freedom of movement from a particular place.”⁹ There are three elements to this offence; an intention to restrict freedom of movement, a complete restriction upon freedom of movement and no lawful authority. Here we will consider the first two of these elements.

⁸ [1961] 1 QB 394.

⁹ [1984] 1 WLR 1172.

Firstly, the claimant (C) must show that there was an intent to restrict their freedom of movement, but this is not an intent to do so without legal authority. In *R v Governor of Brockhill Prison, ex parte Evans*, C had lawfully been imprisoned for criminal conduct, but the prison incorrectly calculated his release date.¹⁰ As such, the court held that C had been falsely imprisoned from the date when he should have been released until the date he actually was released. However, in *Iqbal v Prison Officers Association*, where prison officers went on strike and the governor of the prison ordered the prisoners to be kept in their cells, the Court of Appeal held that there had been no false imprisonment.¹¹ This was because there needs to be a positive act and the C must have a legal right to be released. In this case, not releasing the prisoners was purely an omission and the prisoners had no legal right to be released as there was lawful authority to imprison them.

The second element requires that there is a complete restriction upon C's freedom of movement. In *Walker v Commissioner of Police of the Metropolis*, where a police officer blocked a doorway for a matter of seconds, the Court of Appeal held that this amounted to false imprisonment despite lasting for a very brief period.¹² The key component is that there must be no reasonable means of escape. It is highly likely that the front door where the officer was stood was the only way to leave the premises, hence why there was false imprisonment. The court has further refined this component in the case of *Bird v Jones* where it was held there would be no false imprisonment if C could simply go back the way they came, as this would not amount to a complete restriction upon C's freedom of movement.¹³ In this case, C wanted to walk on one side of the Hammersmith Bridge but it was blocked by the police and C was told to go back the way he came. He could have crossed the bridge from the other side.

¹⁰ [2000] 4 All ER 15.

¹¹ [2010] QB 732.

¹² [2014] EWCA Civ 897.

¹³ (1845) 115 ER 668.

However, the court introduced an exception to the general rule in *Robinson v Balmain New Ferry* where the C entered D's wharf before changing his mind.¹⁴ D required C to pay a small fee in order to leave the wharf. The court held that the D's were entitled to impose a reasonable condition before allowing an individual to leave a place where that person had entered with their own freewill. There is much academic debate regarding whether this is an invasion of civil liberties and this is part of the focus of this article. As Tan explains:

“It is therefore sufficiently clear that at common law a person cannot restrain the liberty of another to enforce a monetary condition as to exit. Such restraint is false imprisonment unless authorised by law. It may be that monetary conditions as to exit, in this context, are never reasonable conditions.”¹⁵

I would agree with Tan that there should not be any restraint on the liberty of a person and such monetary conditions are indeed unfavourable. However, to further understand this argument, we must briefly consider the defences for trespass to the person. These are freely given consent, necessity and self-defence. Here the argument is that C freely got themselves into the situation they find themselves in and so they consented. However, can there be consent if C did not know that a reasonable condition to leave was to be fulfilled? Can't C withdraw their consent? Therefore, I argue that the defence of consent is irrelevant when it comes to this area of the law and that D should not be entitled to impose a condition to leave if C changes their mind.

3. The Problem

In many supermarkets in the present day there are gates both at the entrance of the shop which allow you in but will not allow you back out the way you came in. There are also frequently gates at the exit of the self-checkout section of the shop which are supposed to open as you

¹⁴ [1910] AC 295.

¹⁵ K.F. Tan, 'A misconceived issue in the tort of false imprisonment' (1981) 44 MLR 166.

approach them. However, in situations where an individual goes into a supermarket and decide that they do not want to buy anything, they cannot leave through the way they came in, meaning many individuals will walk through the self-checkout section to leave via that way, with empty hands. If the gates open there is not a problem, but technology can go wrong so there are times when the gates do not open regardless of whether you have bought anything or not. For those who have decided not to buy anything from the shop, is there a reasonable condition for them to buy something in order to leave? For those who have bought something, and the gates still don't open, this can be argued to be a standard case of false imprisonment where the C's freedom of movement is restricted for any given time.

In the time after the Coronavirus pandemic and cost of living crisis, it is more important than ever to encourage individuals to go to high street shops and as this is continuously encouraged, consumer rights are becoming ever more important to business practice and so this issue of imposing a condition to exit can raise questions about whether this aligns with the aims of consumer protection and whether it is indeed ethical. Further, could this raise problems with human rights and the freedom of movement?

We are concerned with the first of these two scenarios where someone is trying to leave the supermarket empty handed, and the gates will not open. There is almost a claim for false imprisonment, except the law in *Robinson* states that the defendant, in this case, the supermarket, can impose reasonable conditions, for instance you must buy something to leave the shop. This conflicts with contract law, as shop items are merely invitations to treat, not obligations to purchase. I may be in the supermarket because of my own free will and thus my consent, but they do not have what I want to buy so is this reasonable for a claim of false imprisonment?

This is a particularly interesting area of law because there have been no cases nor prior academic literature considering this conflict. Two of the main factors in this argument is whether this is a reasonable condition to require customers to buy something, and whether there is an imbalance of rights between supermarkets and their customers.

Turning to the first factor, is there a reasonable condition to require customers to buy something? As already established, there will be scenarios where a shop simply does not have the items we are looking for and so we are forced to leave empty handed, particularly where we are looking to purchase specialist goods such as car parts for a certain brand of car. Requiring customers to satisfy a reasonable condition conflicts with the idea of freedom of contract, which links to the second issue regarding bargaining power between the parties.

The principle of freedom of contract is “the general principle of English law that parties are free to contract as they may think fit”, and the courts have rightfully been reluctant to interfere with this principle even where there is an imbalance in bargaining powers.¹⁶ However, where there is an imbalance in bargaining powers it has been acknowledged that “the customer’s only choice may then be one of accepting those terms or doing without the goods or services in question; and often he cannot in practice do without.”¹⁷

In our scenario, a purchase requirement eliminates freedom of contract, as customers would be forced into transactions without negotiation. It is important, however, to note that there would not be any contract upon entering a shop because at this point the individual would not have provided any consideration. Therefore, customers cannot be said to have entered a contract when entering a shop unless the courts plan to completely rewrite the law of contract. Instead, it is likely that only the tort of trespass could succeed in this area.

¹⁶ Beale, ‘Freedom of Contract’.

¹⁷ Edwin Peel, ‘Introduction’ in Treitel on The Law of Contract (15th edn, 2020).

Either way, an individual does not have a choice to go without in this context because we all require access to supermarkets for food and clothes. Freedom of contract therefore means that a customer cannot be forced into a contract, but in our scenario, it is likely that they will find themselves in a situation where they have no practical choice. Because of this lack of real choice, the agreement to purchase is coercive rather than voluntary which again undermines the freedom of contract and is a cause of concern. This can lead to more people avoiding physical shops and switching to online shopping, which as considered later has both advantages and disadvantages.

Bennett has pointed out that implied consent cannot be inferred in cases where the innocent party with the weaker bargaining power has made it clear that they are not satisfied with the situation, and where there is no realistic alternative due to this weaker bargaining power this cannot equate to consent.¹⁸ Therefore, in our scenario of the customer walking into a supermarket and wanting to walk out empty handed, they are clearly in a weaker bargaining position and would most likely be unsatisfied with a requirement to purchase something.

Whether or not “customers are always right”, forcing purchases on dissatisfied customers with no choice is unfair and contradicts consent. It again emphasises the problem of unequal bargaining power which can be harmful to the relationship of consumer and seller. This strengthens my argument that shops should not impose conditions on leaving the shop. This comes back to trust and customer service which are essential characteristics to maintain a brand image and encourage customers to come back to your shop. If individuals start to develop less trust when entering a contract, people may generally stop being so keen on entering contracts which can have a massive impact because of how contracts are all around us.

¹⁸ Olivia Bennett, ‘Heartbroken by infringement of performer’s rights’ [2013] 24 Ent LR 185.

Some may argue that upon entering a shop the customer impliedly agrees to the terms of that shop, similarly to when we use private car parks. They may go on to argue that this implied consent could be context dependent and could serve to help with security or even operational efficiency. However, it seems to be unreasonable that customers would consent to purchase goods if they cannot find what they would like. A reasonable person would not consider it wrong to leave a shop empty handed and this should be reflected in the law because the law should only prohibit behaviour which is harmful to others in society. The law already protects supermarkets under the criminal law and so additional protection in terms of reasonable conditions to exit are entirely unnecessary. Shops already have lots of ways to ensure security and operational efficiency which can have a less direct impact on the consumer.

Also, from a public policy perspective, if shops were requiring customers to purchase goods, it may mean that individuals are less likely to shop in person and instead turn to online shopping which could have a devastating impact on the high street as we currently know it, and be a problem for the older generation who have less confidence with technology and would prefer to visit shops in person. It is likely, however, that if a court did consider this legal issue that they would not consider a condition to buy something from a shop to be a reasonable condition. This is because unlike *Robinson*, there is no condition to pay to enter a shop and so this also distinguishes supermarkets from private car parks where such a reasonable condition could be proof of payment, usually the parking ticket. Furthermore, imposing a condition to purchase goods could have an impact on consumer trust which could harm the reputation of brands and customer shopping behaviour. Likewise, if customers cannot afford the goods in a shop, this could be an unfair situation for that individual. Again, this could mean less people visit high street shops meaning these will continue to close and the impact this could have on the location and national economy could be large.

For completeness, it is important to mention that there have been cases which have suggested that people cannot falsely imprison someone without statutory authority in order to enforce a civil claim, for instance, in *Sunbolf v Alford*, “innkeepers were not allowed to detain a guest for failure to pay the bill”.¹⁹ However, such scenarios are not relevant to the issue considered in this article as a service has already been obtained, but even then, this is an area of law dealt with both through the law of contract and the criminal law and so there is no need for tort law to be used in such scenarios. Instead, in the case of supermarkets we are considering the situation before a service has been obtained or before a good has been used, but even similar to the point in *Sunbolf*, the criminal law regarding property offences can be employed when someone dishonestly appropriates property without interfering with the rights of innocent customers who wish to leave the shop empty handed. This reflects the idea that there are mechanisms in place to protect supermarkets from the theft of their goods.

4. Technological Advancements

In theory, the idea of these gates is good as it can help prevent criminal behaviour such as theft of items, along with the alarm systems already found in shops. However, to fully achieve this aim the technology must advance significantly. Firstly, as things currently stand there is no evidence to suggest that these gates can differentiate between someone who has paid for items and is trying to leave, someone who wants to leave empty handed and someone who is trying to commit theft. When the technology advances, then the aim of these gates will be more fully fulfilled. This may involve sensors which can pick up whether a barcode has been scanned or not, letting those who have scanned the barcodes out along with those who do not have any property from the supermarket. Individuals attempting to steal the property, on the other hand, would not be able to leave the shop. Although this idea seems to fulfil the aims which the

¹⁹ Gary Lilienthal, Nehaluddin Ahmad and Zainal Amin bin Ayub, ‘Policy considerations for the legality of surrogacy’ [2015] 21 MLJI 88.

supermarkets likely have, it appears that there is a long way to go before the technology can successfully fulfil this aim.

Having said that, we are living in an increasingly digitalised world where there continue to be technological advancements, with so many things going online. It is therefore likely that we may not have to wait long for a more successful solution to come along. In the meantime, shops should consider providing clearer signage or instructions for those customers who may wish to leave the supermarket having not bought anything.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this article has demonstrated that there is a clear conflict between the law of contract and the law of tort in the context of supermarket settings, particularly when it comes to the imposition of conditions on consumers. We have argued that consumers are disadvantaged due to limited freedom of contract and weakened bargaining power, with the result that they are often coerced into accepting terms that they have not voluntarily consented to. This undermines the very foundation of contract law, which is based on mutual consent and voluntary agreement.

Furthermore, the decision in *Robinson* is problematic, as it imposes conditions that remove the autonomy of the parties involved, particularly the consumer, when entering premises under a contractual relationship. This is incompatible with the core principles of contract law, where items on display in a shop should merely constitute an invitation to treat, not an immediate contractual offer. The customer's decision to purchase should still reflect a clear offer and acceptance.

While automated gates offer potential benefits, we have identified that their current technological limitations could result in unintended consequences, such as false imprisonment

claims. Until these systems can be refined to fully meet their objectives without compromising consumers' rights, it is advisable to hold off on their widespread implementation.

Ultimately, the protection of individual autonomy and consent must take precedence in contractual relationships, and the law should evolve to ensure that consumers are not unduly disadvantaged by the conditions imposed upon them in everyday transactions. Future legal developments should focus on striking a balance between advancing technology and upholding fundamental principles of contract law.

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